

The OEW and DW Mass Configurations of the GNBA

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In this document, the properties of hundreds of lumped masses for the generic narrow-body airliner model are listed for two different mass configurations of the aircraft: that with the operating empty weight and that with the design weight. The lumped masses refer to nonstructural parts of the aircraft, like the engines, the crew, the payload, and the fuel, among many others. The listed properties are a complement to the mass properties of the structural components of the aircraft, which were provided separately.

I. Description

The GNBA (Generic Narrow-Body Airliner), originally developed by the author in Ref. [1], can have different distributions of payload and fuel mass in the fuselage and in the wing. Each different distribution of mass is named a “mass configuration” of the vehicle.

One possible mass configuration is that with the *operating empty weight* (OEW), which includes everything that is basically needed for operation, including the crew but only the unusable fuel.

Another possible configuration is that with the *design weight* (DW), including all the masses of the OEW configuration in addition to 13000 kg of payload (passengers, luggage, and cargo) and 6665 kg of fuel.

Whereas the structural masses and moments of inertia can be adequately included using beam mass properties per unit length, the nonstructural masses are included in the structural-dynamic (SD) model using lumped masses. The j th lumped mass has its center of mass C_j rigidly connected to a point K_j in a beam. In this document, the relative position vector from K_j to C_j is given by $\mathbf{r}_{j,0}$ and written in the basic coordinate system 0 of the SD model. The lumped mass has the mass m_j and the inertia matrix $\mathbf{J}_{j,0}$ about its center of mass and with respect to the axes of the basic coordinate system. The inertia matrix can be written as:

$$\mathbf{J}_{j,0} = \begin{bmatrix} I_{xx,j,0} & -I_{xy,j,0} & -I_{xz,j,0} \\ -I_{xy,j,0} & I_{yy,j,0} & -I_{yz,j,0} \\ -I_{xz,j,0} & -I_{yz,j,0} & I_{zz,j,0} \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

Because of their almost negligible contributions to the aircraft inertia matrix, the lumped masses’ products of inertia are assumed null, i.e., $I_{xy,j,0} = I_{xz,j,0} = I_{yz,j,0} = 0$ for all lumped masses.

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The relative position vector can be written as:

$$\mathbf{r}_{j,0} = \begin{bmatrix} r_{x,j,0} & r_{y,j,0} & r_{z,j,0} \end{bmatrix}^T \quad (2)$$

The j th lumped mass is connected to the i th beam of the SD model. The point in the elastic axis to which the lumped mass is rigidly connected is given by the coordinate y_i in the i th beam local coordinate system.

It is then possible to specify the properties of the lumped masses as in Table 1, which corresponds to the OEW mass configuration. The beams and the lumped masses of this mass configuration are shown in Fig. 1.

Table 1 The lumped masses of the GNBA OEW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$r_{x,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{y,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{z,j,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
1	8	2.357	0.616	0	0.118	24.76	0	0	0
2	6	3.494	1.001	0	0.159	49.52	0	0	0
3	7	2.646	-1.005	0	0.118	43.33	0	0	0
4	6	1.941	2.041	0	0.211	37.14	0	0	0
5	7	3.772	0.881	0	0.105	49.52	0	0	0
6	6	1.941	1.541	0	0.211	150.11	0	0	0
7	7	1.383	0.572	0	0.088	121.20	0	0	0
8	7	5.626	0.335	0	0.082	121.20	0	0	0
9	2	6.549	0	0	0.041	43.47	0	0	0
10	4	3.821	0	0	0.085	114.28	0	0	0
11	4	7.792	0	0	0.093	161.93	0	0	0
12	2	2.519	0	0	0.307	225.07	0	0	0
13	4	2.011	0	0	0.092	225.07	0	0	0
14	4	1.207	0	0	0.075	172.27	0	0	0
15	2	1.511	0	0	0.384	338.15	0	0	0
16	4	3.770	0	0	0.010	338.15	0	0	0
17	1	0.498	0	0	-1.200	19.79	0	0	0

Table 1 (Continued) The lumped masses of the GNBA OEW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$r_{x,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{y,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{z,j,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
18	2	0.504	0	0	-0.439	370.40	0	0	0
19	1	1.498	0	0	-0.500	76.20	0	0	0
20	2	4.534	0	0	0.352	370.61	0	0	0
21	2	4.030	0	0	0.291	855.70	267.84	0	186.00
22	2	5.541	0	0	0.275	101.75	0	0	0
23	3	0.272	0	-0.800	-1.200	310.00	0	0	0
24	3	0.272	0	0.800	-1.200	310.00	0	0	0
25	1	7.298	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
26	1	6.485	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
27	1	5.672	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
28	1	4.859	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
29	1	4.046	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
30	1	3.234	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
31	1	2.421	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
32	1	1.608	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
33	1	0.795	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
34	3	0.018	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
35	3	1.288	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
36	3	2.100	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
37	3	2.913	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
38	3	3.726	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
39	3	4.539	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
40	3	5.352	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0

Table 1 (Continued) The lumped masses of the GNBA OEW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$r_{x,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{y,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{z,j,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
41	3	6.164	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
42	3	6.977	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
43	3	7.790	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
44	3	8.603	0	-1.069	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
45	3	9.416	0	-1.049	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
46	3	10.228	0	-1.029	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
47	3	11.041	0	-1.009	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
48	3	11.854	0	-0.989	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
49	3	12.667	0	-0.969	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
50	3	13.480	0	-0.949	-0.562	25.40	0	0	0
51	1	7.298	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
52	1	6.485	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
53	1	5.672	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
54	1	4.859	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
55	1	4.046	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
56	1	3.234	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
57	1	2.421	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
58	1	1.608	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
59	1	0.795	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
60	3	0.018	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
61	3	1.288	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
62	3	2.100	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
63	3	2.913	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0

Table 1 (Continued) The lumped masses of the GNBA OEW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$r_{x,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{y,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{z,j,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
64	3	3.726	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
65	3	4.539	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
66	3	5.352	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
67	3	6.164	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
68	3	6.977	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
69	3	7.790	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
70	3	8.603	0	0.787	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
71	3	9.416	0	0.767	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
72	3	10.228	0	0.747	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
73	3	11.041	0	0.727	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
74	3	11.854	0	0.707	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
75	3	12.667	0	0.687	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
76	3	13.480	0	0.667	-0.562	35.40	0	0	0
77	11	2.618	0.601	0	0	61.90	0	0	0
78	13	3.808	0.756	0	0	49.52	0	0	0
79	9	2.923	-1.391	0	-1.270	143.60	144.80	228.20	228.20
80	9	2.923	-0.233	0	-1.359	2830.00	400.10	2379.00	2379.00
81	9	2.923	0.053	0	0	448.90	18.70	920.00	920.00
82	6	0	2.742	-0.950	0.084	408.00	28.10	28.10	50.00
83	6	0.166	2.423	0	0.147	508.00	173.00	7.62	173.00
84	6	1.830	1.587	0	0.047	103.00	3.51	6.85	7.62
85	2	4.030	0	0	-1.009	136.00	5.88	10.90	5.88
86	2	3.325	0	0	-1.095	174.00	1.81	33.50	33.50

Table 1 (Continued) The lumped masses of the GNBA OEW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$r_{x,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{y,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{z,j,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
87	2	2.519	0	0	-1.193	38.30	1.02	1.02	1.02
88	17	2.357	0.616	0	0.118	24.76	0	0	0
89	15	3.494	1.001	0	0.159	49.52	0	0	0
90	16	2.646	-1.005	0	0.118	43.33	0	0	0
91	15	1.941	2.041	0	0.211	37.14	0	0	0
92	16	3.772	0.881	0	0.105	49.52	0	0	0
93	15	1.941	1.541	0	0.211	150.11	0	0	0
94	16	1.383	0.572	0	0.088	121.20	0	0	0
95	16	5.626	0.335	0	0.082	121.20	0	0	0
96	20	2.618	0.601	0	0	61.90	0	0	0
97	18	2.923	-1.391	0	-1.270	143.60	144.80	228.20	228.20
98	18	2.923	-0.233	0	-1.359	2830.00	400.10	2379.00	2379.00
99	18	2.923	0.053	0	0	448.90	18.70	920.00	920.00
100	15	0	2.742	0.950	0.084	408.00	28.10	28.10	50.00
101	15	0.166	2.423	0	0.147	508.00	173.00	7.62	173.00
102	15	1.830	1.587	0	0.047	103.00	3.51	6.85	7.62

In addition to the lumped masses listed in Table 1, the DW mass configuration also has payload and fuel lumped masses. The payload mass distribution is listed in Table 2, whereas the fuel mass distribution is listed in Table 3. The beams and the lumped masses of this mass configuration are depicted in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1 The GNBA beams and the lumped masses of the OEW mass configuration.

Table 2 The payload lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$r_{x,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{y,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{z,j,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
103	1	7.298	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
104	1	7.298	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
105	1	7.298	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
106	1	7.298	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
107	1	7.298	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
108	1	6.485	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
109	1	6.485	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
110	1	6.485	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78

Table 2 (Continued) The payload lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$r_{x,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{y,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{z,j,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
111	1	6.485	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
112	1	6.485	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
113	1	5.672	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
114	1	5.672	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
115	1	5.672	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
116	1	5.672	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
117	1	5.672	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
118	1	4.859	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
119	1	4.859	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
120	1	4.859	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
121	1	4.859	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
122	1	4.859	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
123	1	4.046	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
124	1	4.046	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
125	1	4.046	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
126	1	4.046	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
127	1	4.046	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
128	1	3.234	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
129	1	3.234	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
130	1	3.234	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
131	1	3.234	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
132	1	3.234	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
133	1	2.421	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78

Table 2 (Continued) The payload lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$r_{x,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{y,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{z,j,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
134	1	2.421	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
135	1	2.421	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
136	1	2.421	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
137	1	2.421	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
138	1	1.608	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
139	1	1.608	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
140	1	1.608	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
141	1	1.608	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
142	1	1.608	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
143	1	0.795	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
144	1	0.795	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
145	1	0.795	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
146	1	0.795	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
147	1	0.795	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
148	3	0.018	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
149	3	0.018	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
150	3	0.018	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
151	3	0.018	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
152	3	0.018	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
153	3	1.288	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
154	3	1.288	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
155	3	1.288	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
156	3	1.288	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78

Table 2 (Continued) The payload lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$r_{x,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{y,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{z,j,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
157	3	1.288	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
158	3	2.100	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
159	3	2.100	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
160	3	2.100	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
161	3	2.100	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
162	3	2.100	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
163	3	2.913	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
164	3	2.913	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
165	3	2.913	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
166	3	2.913	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
167	3	2.913	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
168	3	3.726	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
169	3	3.726	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
170	3	3.726	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
171	3	3.726	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
172	3	3.726	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
173	3	4.539	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
174	3	4.539	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
175	3	4.539	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
176	3	4.539	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
177	3	4.539	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
178	3	5.352	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
179	3	5.352	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78

Table 2 (Continued) The payload lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$r_{x,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{y,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{z,j,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
180	3	5.352	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
181	3	5.352	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
182	3	5.352	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
183	3	6.164	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
184	3	6.164	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
185	3	6.164	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
186	3	6.164	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
187	3	6.164	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
188	3	6.977	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
189	3	6.977	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
190	3	6.977	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
191	3	6.977	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
192	3	6.977	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
193	3	7.790	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
194	3	7.790	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
195	3	7.790	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
196	3	7.790	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
197	3	7.790	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
198	3	8.603	0.000	-1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
199	3	8.603	0.000	-0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
200	3	8.603	0.000	0.225	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
201	3	8.603	0.000	0.787	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
202	3	8.603	0.000	1.350	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78

Table 2 (Continued) The payload lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$r_{x,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{y,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{z,j,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
203	3	9.416	0.000	-1.330	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
204	3	9.416	0.000	-0.767	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
205	3	9.416	0.000	0.205	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
206	3	9.416	0.000	0.767	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
207	3	9.416	0.000	1.330	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
208	3	10.228	0.000	-1.310	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
209	3	10.228	0.000	-0.747	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
210	3	10.228	0.000	0.185	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
211	3	10.228	0.000	0.747	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
212	3	10.228	0.000	1.310	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
213	3	11.041	0.000	-1.290	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
214	3	11.041	0.000	-0.727	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
215	3	11.041	0.000	0.165	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
216	3	11.041	0.000	0.727	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
217	3	11.041	0.000	1.290	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
218	3	11.854	0.000	-1.270	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
219	3	11.854	0.000	-0.707	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
220	3	11.854	0.000	0.145	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
221	3	11.854	0.000	0.707	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
222	3	11.854	0.000	1.270	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
223	3	12.667	0.000	-1.250	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
224	3	12.667	0.000	-0.687	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
225	3	12.667	0.000	0.125	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78

Table 2 (Continued) The payload lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$r_{x,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{y,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{z,j,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
226	3	12.667	0.000	0.687	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
227	3	12.667	0.000	1.250	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
228	3	13.480	0.000	-1.230	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
229	3	13.480	0.000	-0.667	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
230	3	13.480	0.000	0.105	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
231	3	13.480	0.000	0.667	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
232	3	13.480	0.000	1.230	-0.235	75.00	6.90	7.52	3.78
233	1	7.298	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
234	1	6.485	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
235	1	5.672	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
236	1	4.859	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
237	1	4.046	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
238	1	3.234	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
239	1	2.421	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
240	1	1.608	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
241	1	0.795	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
242	3	0.018	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
243	3	1.288	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
244	3	2.100	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
245	3	2.913	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
246	3	3.726	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
247	3	4.539	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
248	3	5.352	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Table 2 (Continued) The payload lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$r_{x,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{y,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{z,j,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
249	3	6.164	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
250	3	6.977	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
251	3	7.790	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
252	3	8.603	0.000	-0.787	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
253	3	9.416	0.000	-0.767	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
254	3	10.228	0.000	-0.747	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
255	3	11.041	0.000	-0.727	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
256	3	11.854	0.000	-0.707	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
257	3	12.667	0.000	-0.687	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
258	3	13.480	0.000	-0.667	1.023	20.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
259	1	7.298	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
260	1	6.485	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
261	1	5.672	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
262	1	4.859	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
263	1	4.046	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
264	1	3.234	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
265	1	2.421	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
266	1	1.608	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
267	1	0.795	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
268	3	0.018	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
269	3	1.288	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
270	3	2.100	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
271	3	2.913	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00

Table 2 (Continued) The payload lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$r_{x,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{y,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{z,j,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
272	3	3.726	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
273	3	4.539	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
274	3	5.352	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
275	3	6.164	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
276	3	6.977	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
277	3	7.790	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
278	3	8.603	0.000	0.787	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
279	3	9.416	0.000	0.767	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
280	3	10.228	0.000	0.747	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
281	3	11.041	0.000	0.727	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
282	3	11.854	0.000	0.707	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
283	3	12.667	0.000	0.687	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
284	3	13.480	0.000	0.667	1.023	30.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
285	1	7.498	0.000	0.000	-1.200	234.00	24.40	11.90	26.50
286	1	6.498	0.000	0.000	-1.200	234.00	24.40	11.90	26.50
287	1	5.498	0.000	0.000	-1.200	234.00	24.40	11.90	26.50
288	1	4.498	0.000	0.000	-1.200	234.00	24.40	11.90	26.50
289	1	3.498	0.000	0.000	-1.200	234.00	24.40	11.90	26.50
290	3	4.502	0.000	0.000	-1.200	260.00	27.10	15.00	31.30
291	3	5.502	0.000	0.000	-1.200	260.00	27.10	15.00	31.30
292	3	6.502	0.000	0.000	-1.200	260.00	27.10	15.00	31.30

Table 3 The fuel lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$r_{x,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{y,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{z,j,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
293	5	0.077	0.000	-1.161	0.271	489.59	23.12	291.81	286.15
294	5	0.077	0.000	-0.878	0.814	489.59	23.12	291.81	286.15
295	5	0.077	0.000	-0.595	1.356	489.59	23.12	291.81	286.15
296	5	0.077	0.000	-0.312	1.898	489.59	23.12	291.81	286.15
297	6	0.077	0.000	-0.172	0.051	143.22	4.22	84.56	80.64
298	6	0.077	0.000	-0.177	0.204	134.30	3.58	77.05	73.75
299	6	0.077	0.000	-0.182	0.358	125.06	3.02	69.98	67.23
300	6	0.077	0.000	-0.187	0.511	116.99	2.52	63.32	61.06
301	6	0.077	0.000	-0.192	0.664	108.61	2.08	57.07	55.22
302	6	0.078	0.000	-0.198	0.817	100.40	1.70	51.21	49.72
303	6	0.078	0.000	-0.203	0.970	92.37	1.37	45.71	44.54
304	6	0.079	0.000	-0.208	1.124	84.52	1.09	40.57	39.66
305	6	0.080	0.000	-0.213	1.277	76.85	0.86	35.77	35.07
306	6	0.081	0.000	-0.218	1.430	69.36	0.66	31.29	30.77
307	6	0.082	0.000	-0.223	1.583	62.04	0.50	27.11	26.75
308	6	0.084	0.000	-0.228	1.736	54.90	0.36	23.24	22.99
309	6	0.087	0.000	-0.233	1.890	47.95	0.26	19.64	19.48
310	6	0.090	0.000	-0.239	2.043	41.17	0.18	16.31	16.21
311	6	0.095	0.000	-0.244	2.196	34.57	0.12	13.23	13.18
312	6	0.103	0.000	-0.249	2.349	28.15	0.08	10.39	10.37
313	6	0.114	0.000	-0.255	2.503	21.90	0.05	7.77	7.77
314	6	0.135	0.000	-0.261	2.656	15.84	0.03	5.36	5.37
315	6	0.162	0.000	-0.267	2.809	10.10	0.01	3.22	3.23

Table 3 (Continued) The fuel lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$r_{x,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{y,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{z,j,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
316	6	0.169	0.000	-0.274	2.962	4.93	0.01	1.51	1.51
317	6	0.131	0.000	-0.281	3.115	0.98	0.00	0.30	0.30
318	14	-0.077	0.000	-1.161	0.271	489.59	23.12	291.81	286.15
319	14	-0.077	0.000	-0.878	0.814	489.59	23.12	291.81	286.15
320	14	-0.077	0.000	-0.595	1.356	489.59	23.12	291.81	286.15
321	14	-0.077	0.000	-0.312	1.898	489.59	23.12	291.81	286.15
322	15	-0.077	0.000	-0.172	0.051	143.22	4.22	84.56	80.64
323	15	-0.077	0.000	-0.177	0.204	134.30	3.58	77.05	73.75
324	15	-0.077	0.000	-0.182	0.358	125.06	3.02	69.98	67.23
325	15	-0.077	0.000	-0.187	0.511	116.99	2.52	63.32	61.06
326	15	-0.077	0.000	-0.192	0.664	108.61	2.08	57.07	55.22
327	15	-0.078	0.000	-0.198	0.817	100.40	1.70	51.21	49.72
328	15	-0.078	0.000	-0.203	0.970	92.37	1.37	45.71	44.54
329	15	-0.079	0.000	-0.208	1.124	84.52	1.09	40.57	39.66
330	15	-0.080	0.000	-0.213	1.277	76.85	0.86	35.77	35.07
331	15	-0.081	0.000	-0.218	1.430	69.36	0.66	31.29	30.77
332	15	-0.082	0.000	-0.223	1.583	62.04	0.50	27.11	26.75
333	15	-0.084	0.000	-0.228	1.736	54.90	0.36	23.24	22.99
334	15	-0.087	0.000	-0.233	1.890	47.95	0.26	19.64	19.48
335	15	-0.090	0.000	-0.239	2.043	41.17	0.18	16.31	16.21
336	15	-0.095	0.000	-0.244	2.196	34.57	0.12	13.23	13.18
337	15	-0.103	0.000	-0.249	2.349	28.15	0.08	10.39	10.37
338	15	-0.114	0.000	-0.255	2.503	21.90	0.05	7.77	7.77

Table 3 (Continued) The fuel lumped masses of the GNBA DW mass configuration.

Mass index j	Connects to beam	y_i [m]	$r_{x,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{y,j,0}$ [m]	$r_{z,j,0}$ [m]	m_j [kg]	$I_{xx,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{yy,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]	$I_{zz,j,0}$ [kg·m ²]
339	15	-0.135	0.000	-0.261	2.656	15.84	0.03	5.36	5.37
340	15	-0.162	0.000	-0.267	2.809	10.10	0.01	3.22	3.23
341	15	-0.169	0.000	-0.274	2.962	4.93	0.01	1.51	1.51
342	15	-0.131	0.000	-0.281	3.115	0.98	0.00	0.30	0.30

Fig. 2 The GNBA beams and the lumped masses of the DW mass configuration.

References

- [1] Guimarães Neto, A. B., "Flight dynamics of flexible aircraft using general body axes: a theoretical and computational study," Ph.D. thesis, Instituto Tecnológico de Aeronáutica, São José dos Campos, Brazil, 2014.